

Effect of tillage method, height of rice stubble, and insecticide on bean fly population infesting cowpeas planted after lowland rice. IRRI, 1977.

Tillage	Rice stubble	Bean fly counts ^a						
		Adults (no./18-m row)			Larvae + pupae (no./25 plants)		Infested plants (%)	
		5 DE	10 DE	15 DE	21 DE		21 DE	
		Untreated plots			Treated plots ^b	Untreated plots	Treated plots	Untreated plots
Plowed and harrowed twice	Plowed under	15 a	12 a	1 a	10 ab	19 a	52 bc	88 a
Furrows plowed between rice rows	Cut to 1 cm	8 a	2 a	1 a	5 bc	9 abc	37 cd	62 b
Furrows plowed between rice rows	30–40 cm ^c	1 b	2 b	1 a	5 bc	6 bc	30 de	29 de
No tillage; seed dibbled in rows	30–40 cm ^c	0 b	2 b	2 b	3c	3 c	17 e	20 de

^aWithin counting dates means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level. DE = days after crop emergence.

^b0.25 kg cyanophenphos (Surecide 25 EC) a.i./ha sprayed at 5 and 15 DE.

^cRatoon crop.

plots received insecticide sprays (Surecide 25 EC) at 5 and 15 days after emergence at the rate of 0.25 kg a.i./ha. The trial was replicated three times.

The population of the bean fly *Ophiomyia phaseoli* was low in plots with standing rice stubble and where the rice had ratooned (see table). In the early growth stages of cowpeas, the rice stubble evidently interfered with the host-seeking responses of the bean fly. At 5 days after cowpea emergence (DE), significantly fewer adults were observed ovipositing

in cowpeas among the 30- to 40-cm rice stubble. At 10 DE bean fly oviposition was restricted to the rice that had ratooned in the treatment where stubble was cut to ground level.

As forms of cultural control, rice stubble and ratoon rice were as effective as insecticide protection in preventing bean fly buildup at the crucial early stages of cowpea growth. At 21 DE no significant difference was observed between plots that had been treated with insecticide and those that had not been

in terms of the number of larvae and pupae per 25 plants and the percentage of infested plants in 30–40 cm stubble. The bean fly population was high in the untreated plots that received the high tillage treatment (19 larvae + pupae/25 plants and 88% infested plants). Infestation levels were intermediate in the plots where stubble was cut (9 larvae + pupae/25 plants and 62% infested plants).

Promising varieties of rainfed legumes grown at zero tillage after paddy rice

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The inclusion of upland crops such as legumes increases overall crop productivity in rice-based cropping systems. Legumes, particularly soybeans, mung beans, and cowpeas, augment the nutritional output of cropping patterns. To ensure the success of subsequent cropping patterns, scientists must first identify high yielding varieties of suitable legumes.

Ten promising varieties each of soybeans, mung beans, and cowpeas were evaluated at zero tillage under rainfed conditions after a crop of paddy rice at IRRI in mid-December 1976. The legumes were planted immediately after rice harvest to capitalize on the

Origin and agronomic data of promising varieties of soybeans, mung beans, and cowpeas planted after paddy rice at zero tillage under rainfed conditions. IRRI, 1976–77 dry season.

Crop, variety	Origin	Seed yield (t/ha)	Yield advantage over check (%)	Maturity (days)	Ht (cm)
<i>Soybeans</i>					
Kuro daizu	Japan	1.77	88	19	59
Bethel	USA	1.25	33	81	40
UPLB-SY 2	Philippines	1.22	30	76	49
Multivar 80	USA	1.21	29	77	43
TK 5 (check)	Taiwan	0.94	–	80	36
<i>Mung beans</i>					
CES 1D-21	Philippines	1.43	25	78	61
EG Glabrous # 3	Philippines	1.35	18	73	69
CES 55	Philippines	1.24	9	72	78
Dau Mo	Vietnam	1.22	7	73	69
CES 87 (check)	Philippines	1.14	–	71	18
<i>Cowpeas</i>					
EG #3	Philippines	1.47	30	75	51
EG #2	Philippines	1.44	27	74	49
TVU 4-b-b-10-b	IITA ^a , Nigeria	1.29	14	75	65
All season	USA	1.18	4	75	78
EG # 1 (check)	Philippines	1.13	–	76	77

^aInternational Institute of Tropical Agriculture.

substantial supply of residual moisture and the low initial weed population. Rice was cut close to the ground and gramoxone herbicide was applied. Seed of soybeans and mung beans were dibbled. Plots were weeded twice by hand. Insects were adequately controlled by two sprayings of carbofuran, followed by three sprayings of methomyl whenever initial pest damage was observed.

Varieties that yielded significantly higher than others were soybean Kuro daizu; mung beans CES 1 D-21, E.G. Glabrous #3, CES 55, and Dau Mo; and cowpeas E.G. #3, E.G. #2, and TVu4-b-b-10-b (see table). Yields were almost as high as those of the same crops grown with good tillage under upland conditions. Yields of the high yielding legumes ranged from 4 to 88% higher

than those of the checks. All crops matured within 71 to 81 days; mung beans generally matured earliest, followed by cowpeas, then soybeans. Soybean plants were shorter and matured earlier than usual because of photoperiod reaction. The cowpea crop, which was not mulched, did not grow as tall as mung beans. The mung bean crop, which was mulched, had a better supply of moisture.

A novel strategy of intercropping in traditional lowland rice fields to maximize food production

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Intercropping is well suited for small farmers who seek to maximize production by having one or more crops on every square meter of land all year round. Little work has been done on intercropping in lowland rice fields where the traditional practice is to raise two or more crops of rice in tandem sequence. The feasibility of raising high-value crops in the traditional wetlands was studied during the rabi season (Feb.–May) of 1976–77 at the Rice Research Station, Pattambi.

A rice field of 574.8 sq m was divided into two parts. In one (245.5 sq m), the rice variety Triveni was transplanted. In the other part (329.3 sq m) the intercropping study was conducted. Ash gourd, cucumber, okra, and cowpea were planted on raised beds 16.5 m long, 1.5 m wide, and 10 cm high. The distance between two beds was 2 m. Four such beds occupied 99 sq m. On all sides of the beds, Triveni was transplanted as in the other portion of the field. The net area of rice in the intercropped field was 230.3 sq m.

Cucumber and ash gourd were raised in polythene cups and 18- to 20-day-old seedlings were transplanted in the raised beds immediately after planting rice to reduce the cropping time in the main field. Okra was seeded directly between each two cucumber and ash gourd seedlings. Cowpea was sown on the borders of all beds. Vegetables were not irrigated, as sufficient moisture was

available in their root zones by capillary rise from the rice fields where the soil was kept under shallow submergence (2–5 cm).

The rice crop yielded 107.8 kg grain (4.4 t/ha) and 169.0 kg straw (6.9 t/ha), while the rice crop surrounding the vegetables produced 96.1 kg grain (4.2 t/ha) and 139.1 kg straw (6.1 t/ha). Vegetable production from the

intercropped area was 307.1 kg (31.0 t/ha). Thus, the total food production with intercropping was 12.24 tons vs. 4.39 tons from the sole crop of rice, an increase in overall productivity of 170.8%. The study indicates a tremendous potential for increasing food production from wetland rice fields. The investigation is being continued on a large scale at Pattambi.

Machinery development & testing.

Manually operated diaphragm pump developed at BRRI

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(BRRI) has developed a manually operated diaphragm pump for low-cost irrigation. The pump has an average discharge capacity of 8,925 liters/hour and an optimum lifting head of 4.65 m (see table). It is made of steel sheets.

The cost of making one unit is roughly Tk 545 (US\$37) — low enough that poor

Upward movement of the handle causes the pump's diaphragm to expand and thus draw water from a well or a stream through a common manifold and into the pump chamber. Compression of the diaphragm forces the water from the chamber. Directional movement of water is controlled by a set of simple flapper valves on the inlet and outlet side.